

Validation of the Poisson Box Sampling Method for Dispersion Fuel Analysis in RMC Code

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ABSTRACT

With growing interest in Accident Tolerant Fuels (ATF) such as dispersed Fully Ceramic Micro-Encapsulated (FCM) fuel, implicit (annealed-disorder) modeling processes are increasing important in the precise simulation of particle transport in stochastic media. In Reactor Monte Carlo (RMC) Code, a continuous-energy Reactor Monte Carlo neutron and photon transport code currently being developed by the Department of Engineering Physics at Tsinghua University, Beijing, current implicit modeling techniques include the Chord Length Sampling (CLS) method, as well as the Semi-Implicit CLS (SICLS) Method. The Poisson Box Sampling (PBS) methods are a new family of algorithms aimed at accurately modelling particle transport through binary Markov mixtures. In this work, we examine the validity of PBS against explicit (quenched-disorder) models and CLS for dispersion fuel, particularly for spherical particles suspended in a matrix. We vary the particle radii as well as the packing fraction of the dispersion fuel while maintaining the overall fuel configuration, to understand how PBS performs under various realistic modelling conditions. Using the results of the explicit modelling methods as a benchmark, we observe that PBS is shown to perform better than CLS across various dispersion fuel modelling conditions, with a much higher computational efficiency compared to the explicit modelling methods.

Keywords: Stochastic Media, Dispersion Fuel, Poisson Box Sampling, Reactor Monte Carlo

1. INTRODUCTION

Stochastic geometry is a key aspect of numerous nuclear reactors, especially in next-generation reactors. They occur, for instance, as stochastic and dynamically turbulent molten fuel in Molten-Salt Reactors (MSRs) [1], randomly distributed fuel pebble distributions or micro-fuel particulate in dispersion fuel in High Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactors (HTGRs) [2], or even non-homogeneous radiation shields in most nuclear reactor systems [3]. As such, the modelling of stochastic geometry is of particular significance in the precise simulation of particle transport codes. In the context of dispersion fuel, modelling methods can typically be categorized into explicit methods (also known as quenched-disorder models) where a static distribution of particulate are referenced during neutron transport, or implicit methods (also known as annealed-disorder models) where the particulate are generated on-the-fly.

In Reactor Monte Carlo (RMC) Code, a continuous-energy Reactor Monte Carlo neutron and photon transport code currently being developed by the Department of Engineering Physics at Tsinghua University, Beijing [4], current implicit modeling techniques include the Chord Length Sampling (CLS) method [5, 6, 7], as well as the Semi-Implicit CLS (SICLS) Method [8]. The CLS method is a highly robust modelling method for simulating dispersion fuel, and the method provides significant improvements over explicit modelling methods in terms of computational efficiency. The SICLS method improves

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upon the CLS method, by reducing the inaccuracies of CLS during the simulation of fuels containing materials of high scattering and absorbing properties due to its memoryless nature [5, 8], whilst minimizing any increase on computational expense [9]. However, both implicit modelling methods in RMC code are currently only suitable for the modelling of spherical particles; there is a need for methods capable of simulating heterogeneous, non-uniform stochastic media such as boiling water reactor (BWR) two-phase coolant or heterogeneous concrete in radiation shielding. While there have been multiple attempts to realize CLS for three-dimensional particle transport [10, 7], these methods are unable to be generalized for all types of stochastic media, and would require on-the-fly sampling of chord lengths from unknown statistical distributions. In non-Markovian stochastic media, especially in the presence of materials of high absorbing and scattering properties, the chord length distribution can only be approximated at best, with large margin for inaccuracy.

The Poisson Box Sampling (PBS) method aims to overcome this – due to the observation by Larmier et al [11] that the physical observables related to particle transport in the quasi-isotropic Poisson tessellations (based off Cartesian boxes) is nearly identical to those calculated in isotropic Poisson tessellations [12], it has been shown that as long as the material composition is provided, the PBS method can be used to approximate particle transport in heterogeneous, non-uniformly structured stochastic media [11]. While previous works have verified the PBS method against existing benchmarks, such as those of Adams, Larsen and Pomraning [6], there has been less literature regarding the validity of the method when applied to the simulation of dispersion fuel. Hence, this paper attempts to validate the PBS method for such modelling scenarios.

This paper will be organized into the following sections. In Section 2, we describe the methodology of the PBS method, including the general equations we utilized to modify the PBS method for modelling the statistically isotropic nature of dispersion fuel mixtures. We thus examine the accuracy and effectiveness of PBS against that of CLS and the explicit Random Sequential Addition (RSA) and Discrete Element Methods (DEM) in Section 3, to validate the PBS method for dispersion fuel analysis. Section 4 discusses the limitations and future work for this body of research. Section 5 thus summarizes the findings and concludes the paper.

2. METHODOLOGY OF THE POISSON BOX SAMPLING METHOD

2.1. Methodology for PBS-1

To ensure that the paper remains self-contained, we first describe the PBS Method in its entirety in RMC code. For the purposes of this paper, we will primarily discuss PBS in the context of neutron transport through dispersion fuel. The PBS methods developed by Larmier et al [11] are a family of Monte Carlo methods utilized to derive ensemble-averaged observables for particle transport in Markovian n -ary mixtures. The method consists primarily of sampling on-the-fly boxes, whose side lengths are randomly sampled from exponential distributions with given averages. Two variants were proposed: PBS-1, where random boxes were generated, and PBS-2, where the memory of the last generated box was retained as well, to account for spatial effects. In this paper, we will focus mainly on PBS-1.

- Step 0: With the given average chord length ($\Lambda_\alpha, \Lambda_\beta$) for each material (α, β) in the binary stochastic medium, derive the correlation length of the geometry via $\Lambda = (1 - p_\alpha)\Lambda_\alpha$ or $\Lambda = p_\alpha\Lambda_\beta$, where p_α and p_β are the material fractions of α and β respectively.
- Step 1: Initialize each particle from its source, along with its specified initial positional coordinates and angles. Generate a random Cartesian box around the particle. The box is defined by the material label i (sampled from the given overall material composition) and its spatial position, given by the center coordinates of the box (x_c, y_c, z_c), and its side lengths (l_x, l_y, l_z). For the primary box, three pairs of random numbers (Δ_x^+, Δ_x^-), (Δ_y^+, Δ_y^-) and (Δ_z^+, Δ_z^-) are sampled from independent exponential distributions of average $3\Lambda/2$. The center and side lengths of the box are thus defined as:

$$x_c = x + (\Delta_x^+ - \Delta_x^-)/2; y_c = y + (\Delta_y^+ - \Delta_y^-)/2; z_c = z + (\Delta_z^+ - \Delta_z^-)/2 \quad (1)$$

$$l_x = \Delta_x^+ + \Delta_x^-; l_y = \Delta_y^+ + \Delta_y^-; l_z = \Delta_z^+ + \Delta_z^- \quad (2)$$

- Step 2: Three distances are computed using the current particle position and directions: the distance to next physical boundary l_b ; the distance to collision l_c (determined by the macroscopic cross section Σ_i of the selected box material i from Step 1, where l_c is drawn from an exponential distribution with an average of $1/\Sigma_i$); and the distance to box interface l_i , calculated with the given positions of the box surfaces.
- Step 3: The minimum distance amongst l_b , l_c , and l_i is selected, and the particle accordingly moves this selected distance along its current direction. If the minimum is l_b , the particle hits the physical boundary, and the direction of the particle will then be updated upon the imposition of any reflective properties of this boundary. If the minimum is l_c , the particle undergoes a collision event at its new position, and material properties are selected as per the material label i of the box. If the minimum is l_i , the particle intersects with the surface of the current box – a new box is generated as per Step 4, and the new box then becomes the current box. If the particle survives without capture, the algorithm returns to Step 2.
- Step 4: A new random spacing Δ_{new} is first drawn from an exponential distribution with average $3\Lambda/2$. The intersected surface determines which surface of the box are retained and which are discarded or replaced. For instance, if the intersected surface of the box is perpendicular to the x-axis, a new box is thus generated, with the length of this new box along the x-axis $l_x = \Delta_{new}$, whilst retaining the other box parameters l_y , l_z , y_c , and z_c . x_c is then updated, with $x_c = x_{particle} + l_x \cdot w_x / \|w_x\|$ where w_x represents the particle direction along the x-axis. Effectively, if the particle collides with the upper x-surface of the box, the upper x-surface is thus treated as the lower x-surface of the new box, and the upper x-surface of the new box is treated as $\Delta_z^+ + l_x$.

For more detail regarding other PBS variants, as well as how PBS matches up against CLS for a fixed-source benchmark for ensemble-averaged variables, the reader is referred to Larmier et al [11].

2.2. Average Chord Length for Distribution of Mono-spherical particulate

The PBS method as described in Section 2.1 is suitable for simulating binary stochastic media, so long as the parameters for chord length (or correlation length Λ), material fractions p_α and p_β , and material composition (α, β) are known and provided. As such, we draw upon previous literature to bridge PBS to apply it towards simulating a particle distribution of mono-spheres, similar to that of Tri-structural Isotropic (TRISO) particles suspended in a matrix, such as those commonly found in dispersion fuel. For a mixture of statistically isotropic mixtures, Torquato et al [9] defines the mean chord length as

$$\Lambda_\alpha = \frac{4p_\alpha}{A/V} = \frac{4(1 - p_\beta)}{A/V} \quad (3)$$

where Λ_α is the average chord length in material alpha for a binary stochastic medium, and p_α refers to the material fraction of material α in a heterogeneous binary stochastic medium. In the context of dispersion fuel, A refers to the surface area of a single spherical particle, which in this case are assumed to be mono-sized spheres, V refers to the volume of a single particle, and N refers to the number density of the spheres. Both A and V are themselves defined by the radius of the spherical particle R . Equations 4, and 5 describe the general equations for A , V , and A/V , and equation 6 describes the derived simplified relationship between chord length (for a neutron traversing the mono-spherical particle) and the mono-sphere radius, as described in Torquato et al [9].

$$A = 4\pi \cdot R^2, V = \frac{4}{3}\pi \cdot R^3, N = \frac{p_\alpha}{V} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Total Interfacial area per unit volume} = \frac{A}{V} = N \cdot A = \frac{3p_\alpha}{R} \quad (5)$$

$$\Lambda_\alpha = \frac{4p_\alpha}{A/V} = \frac{4R}{3} \quad (6)$$

However, this average chord length is defined primarily for particle transport within the mono-sphere itself. The matrix of a dispersion fuel possesses a different average chord length, which is described by equation 7, where ϕ refers to the volumetric fraction of the particles.

$$\Lambda_m = \frac{4R}{3} \cdot \frac{1 - \phi}{\phi} \quad (7)$$

The average chord length of each respective material can then be utilized to obtain the average overall chord length Λ of the exponential distribution that determines the box lengths via equation 8 [11].

$$\Lambda = \Lambda_m \cdot \phi = \Lambda_p \cdot (1 - \phi) \quad (8)$$

Hence, for the simulation of a dispersion fuel mixture comprising of two distinct materials, the correlation length as defined in Section 2.1 can be replaced with the average chord length as defined in 6. However, it must be noted that this can only be applied to binary stochastic media, or in the case of dispersion fuel, mono-sized spherical particulate made of a singular type of material – this modified PBS method thus cannot be applied to multi-layered, multi-material particles such as TRISO particulate suspended in a graphite matrix, for example.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The algorithm, as a function of RMC code, was run on a AMD Ryzen Threadripper 3990X 64-Core Processor, with only a single thread being used for all computations. For each set of calculations, 100 runs are taken, and the ensemble-averaged results of these 100 runs are compared. For all the tests discussed in this Section, a simplified cuboidal dispersion fuel model was set up, and the model was simulated under RMC's critical calculation module. Table I illustrates the parameters describing the cuboidal dispersion fuel model, as well as experimental variables such as the number of neutrons and the number of inactive/active cycles.

Table I. Experimental Parameters

Parameter	Value
Length/Height/Width	20.0 cm
Particle Packing Fraction	25-50%
Particle radius	0.5 cm
Particle material	UO ₂
Matrix material	Graphite
Number of neutrons	100000
Inactive/Active Cycles	100/100
Boundary Condition	Full Reflection

The particle packing fraction was varied between 25% to 50%, while the particle radius was maintained at 0.5 cm. The model was simulated firstly using explicit modelling methods – primarily the Random

Sequential Addition (RSA) Method, as well as being coupled with the Discrete Element Method (DEM) for packing fractions above that of the saturation limit of RSA [8, 13]. The model was then simulated using CLS and PBS, and the results were then compared against those obtained from the explicit modelling methods. Fig. 1 describes the comparison between the obtained k_{inf} values.

Figure 1. k_{inf} Against Packing Fraction.

In this experiment, the RSA/DEM methods are used as the benchmarks for k_{inf} due to their highly accurate nature, as particles are explicitly generated without any loss in fidelity, unlike the CLS and PBS methods, which can be said to be approximations of the explicit methods. As shown in Fig. 1, PBS shows significantly higher agreement with the results derived from the explicit modelling methods compared to CLS. This is in line with observations from Larmier et al [11], as the PBS-1 method tends to show higher agreement with explicit modelling solutions over those computed in CLS. This observation only increases as the particle packing fraction increases. At the 50% packing fraction, the k_{inf} values for RSA, PBS and CLS are 1.170748 (± 0.000143), 1.171196 (± 0.000116), and 1.147911 (± 0.000130) respectively, with RSA-CLS having a much larger difference of 118 sigma compared to the RSA-PBS difference of 2 sigma.

To supplement these computations, as well as to examine Larmier et al's results regarding the computational efficiency of PBS, we attempted to examine the overall computational time for each method. These values were taken as a whole; as the RSA/DEM methods generate particle distributions independently of neutron transport, but PBS/CLS generate stochastic media on-the-fly, the overall computational time was compared, to ensure that nuances and discrepancies due to the algorithmic differences in stochastic media generation were not exacerbated. Fig. 2 depicts the comparison between the overall computational time values obtained between the methods.

Similar to the results observed in Larmier et al [11], the PBS method is relatively similar to CLS in terms of computational expense. When both implicit methods are compared to their explicit counterparts, it remains obvious that the implicit methods are much more computationally efficient. This can also be attributed in part to the RSA's saturation limit of 38% [8], where DEM was coupled with RSA for the simulation of particles. As such, the significant increase in computational expense beyond the packing fraction of 38% can be accounted for by the incredibly high computational expense required by DEM.

While the experiment as described in Figs. 1 and 2 allowed us to understand the performance of the

Figure 2. Overall Computational Time Against Packing Fraction.

PBS method for different packing fractions, there is still a research gap regarding the efficiency of PBS for different particle radii, or indirectly, different average chord lengths. We utilize the same parameters presented in Table I, except where the packing fraction was maintained at 50%, and the particle radius was instead varied between 0.4 to 0.8 cm.

Figure 3. k_{inf} Against Particle Radius.

Fig. 3 describes the comparison between the k_{inf} values obtained between the methods. Similar to the

observations made from Fig. 1, PBS is shown to produce packing fractions of higher fidelity compared to CLS, against the results of the explicit modelling methods. Fig. 4 illustrates the comparison between the overall computational time values obtained between the methods. It can be seen that the RSA method is extremely computationally expensive compared to CLS and PBS, where the computational times between the two implicit methods are very much comparable. Furthermore, this computational expense increases significantly as the particle radius grows smaller, highlighting the significance of PBS as an accurate and computationally efficient method for complex stochastic media systems, or in the presence of dispersion fuel with large numbers of particulate.

Figure 4. Overall Computational Time Against Particle Radius.

4. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In theory, the PBS-1 method is particularly effective for Markovian stochastic media, and suffers in the presence of materials of high scattering and absorbing properties. This is particularly challenging for the simulation of stochastic media that are structured primarily for the purpose of absorption or scattering, such as heterogeneous, non-uniform concrete in radiation shields. Hence, adapting PBS for non-Markovian stochastic media remains an important avenue of research. Furthermore, other PBS variants such as PBS-2 offer better consideration for the spatial correlations between boxes, making them more effective at simulating stochastic media where memory effects are more significant. These methods may fare better at simulating dispersion fuel with non-overlapping spherical particulate.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this body of work, the PBS method proposed by Larmier et al was enabled on RMC code, and the validity of the PBS method was analysed by comparing the criticality results against CLS and RSA/DEM. It was found that PBS produced k_{inf} results that displayed excellent agreement with results derived from the explicit modelling methods, and with higher accuracy compared to CLS. Furthermore, PBS was shown to have excellent computational efficiency, being nearly on par with CLS. The overall results indicate a successful enablement of PBS in RMC, as well as illustrate PBS's capabilities in terms

of simulating neutron transport through binary spherical particle distributions. Future work will focus on further rounds of validation with different test parameters, as well as exploring the possibility of utilizing PBS for the simulation of non-Markovian stochastic media.

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